

THE HIDDEN BATTLE OF THE SLAVS: THE RED-WAR OF TRANSNISTRIA

by

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Abstract:

Completing its third decade of existence, the fall of Soviet Union was one of the biggest evolutionary structuring and redeveloping phase for the Eastern Europe. The enormous seventy-four year old Soviet Union, which dominated the political scene all around the globe, variating and moving into the cold battle with the United States, causing political changes in several countries including Iran or be it directly impacting the structural changes in the political system of several countries including that of the Democratic People's Republic of Korea also known as North Korea as well as indirectly supporting the conflicts outside its country and acting as a supporting cause to several revolutions, the collapse of the Big State not only indicted the change and reformation in the Eastern Europe, but also impacted in several changes that were invited which included the economic and market reforms. While this global phenomenon was taking place, the Soviet Union was slowly breaking down into smaller places which included several breakaway countries. Over the period of time, there have been several instances wherein the efforts have been made by the Russian Federation which was the original USSR(Union of Soviet Socialist Republic) which included wars and locations that extended within the Union of the Russian Federation as well as the states attached to it who were trying to breakaway. The Republic of Moldova is a constituent of the Russian Populations which consists of more than a quarter of the citizens in the special of Transnistria which falls on the border of Ukraine and Moldova. The majority of the 28% Russians who constitute the independent state supported the idea of holding the region separate from the identity which they felt were getting attacked by the "Moldovian Republic" was lead out as the next battle for

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freedom which involved the rebellion and one of the fiercest battles fought in the region. The Article talks about the premises which pertains to the battle of 1992 and the outcome of the war. The Article talks about the present situation in the region with the ongoing conflict or Special Military Operation in Ukraine has the effect on the region. Apart from the importance, the Article tries to highlight the importance of holding such regions as well as mention of the hardships one might face in the region and the political outcomes. The Article concludes the importance which entails itself in the form of representation around the world and how the war has impacted the structure of functioning of people around the world.

Introduction:

The development of the Eastern Europe has been a sign of remarkable change that can be observed over a period of three centuries. In numerous battles and fights, the Balkans, Baltics and the Caucasus which led to series of tensions in the region. Apart from externally hurting itself through the ruling of regime of the mighty Ottomans who considerably had power over the Balkan for almost two centuries. The Russians under the mighty Peter the Great had established the long and widespread Russian empire which considered itself of utmost importance in terms of providing a solitude towards preventing the massive loss of the Slavic identity as well as expanding the power and potential of the greater Slavs all around the globe. The fight for the idea of survival in the Balkan in the early twentieth century leading to the first World War or be it the mighty World War Two which came in to conclude such imperialistic beliefs in the whole of the European Continent and fry towards an idea of democracy which enlisted the true reposition of faith in the people who were the mighty rulers. The time changed quickly pertaining around the circumstances wherein people fought incredible battles and believed in the changes for the best and at the earliest. However, it must be known to the fact that the ideal structure for the Eastern European nations were to hold their uniqueness as to what they believed to have created separate nations with their individualistic approach as well as their integrity in terms of providing a linguistic change which can be called to be of a sharp cut-out from the invariable hassles and struggles they had faced in the past. The best identical structuralism can be seen in the creation of individual states of Czechoslovakia, Yugoslavia and the mighty Union of Soviet Socialist and Republic (USSR) which expanded its base by allowing the existence of puppet Government in the countries such as East Germany, Cuba (claimed by the critiques of the USSR). The identity of such state has been made to conduce its structure and beliefs which include the dispute which commenced on the North-Western

sector of the Black Sea. The idea of Moldovan identity which has had its fair share of fight during its Soviet Regime which was responsible for the conduct of such actions that would result in harming the longing identity of the two based community. Over the period of time, there have been several other battles and fights which finally led to a confrontation which has held its three identical warfare which held a nature that was sorted into three main categories which include the Political, Economical and Social structuring. The identity was sorted but was finally held out its positioning once there was the establishment of the conflict which held the Transnistria out of the Moldovan and Romanian power hubs.

History:

The battlefield which held the small entitlement to the historical power mongering leaders who considered the identity creation to be utmost importance which holds the structuring and the beliefs that was segregated by the leaders of the countries who did not understand the sentiments of the Moldovans back in the days.³ The commencement of the short landing violations of border came in with the first sign of agreement which took place between the Soviet and the third reich which came to be known as the Molotov- Ribbentrop Pact which was impactful in terms of giving the structure and the identity to the conquest of the regions and promulgated the World War two on to the next level.⁴ The entailment of the pact recognized the partition of Poland and other regions that were responsible for holding the region in such a manner. The separation of the Bessarabian region was called of and declared null and void by the Moldovan Government in 1991 after its independence. The belief was that the region is part of the Undivided Romania that was shared by the Moldovans. The structure was declarative in terms as it sought for the extension of the whole of Moldova including the region of Transnistria.

Indian Journal of Contemporary
Legal and Social Issues

Linguistic Chauvinism: The Bone of Contention

The majority of the disputes which can be observed in certain political country pertaining to the confrontation especially in the region of Europe is the identity of language. The majority speaking population living in the region of Transnistria were consisting of the Russian and Ukrainian identity which constituted up to the majority of the land.⁵ The identity was willing to defy as the laws which were implemented by the Moldovan Parliament. The revolt of

³ The dissimilar identification of the two regimes, Biblioteca National a Romaini, 1941.

⁴ Molotov-Ribbentrop Pact, 1939

⁵ The Transnistrian Census of 1989.

believing and holding the identity of the linguistic power took towards the Political battlefield that was being held from both the sides. Apart from the collateral structure that was of political in nature, the Russian speaking majors in the region decided to constitute the ideal warfare and prepared for the conflict as the sentiment which is meant to control and hold their identity. The contention did not just confine to the idea of the Russians and Ukrainians retaining their identity, but it was a bigger picture that wanted to remove the domination of the areas which belonged to the speakers of the land as well as become inclined towards providing a way that would be helpful in creating the best possible outcome. For one, it can be stated that the war was more inclined towards the Ethnic-political rivalry along with the dupe functioning of the political erotism that has been seen in the past, wherein the cases of warfare fringed upon the power actions and the determination to hinder the smooth flow of the usage of language in the society which would perceive and pertain to the ethnic Slavs of the Eastern Europe. One cannot called the Battle a long one but rather a longing one as one can say that the Ethnic Russians were not the ones to consider the rule of implementation of Majoritarianism.

The Military Conflict:

For one to fight out the battles and understand their essence, the final nail on the coffin comes through the approval of the outside Government which realizes and supports the cause of the Rebellion against any of the action to protect the rights of the ethnic speaking people of the land. The laws passed by the Moldovan Parliament related to the language and the importance of the usage of the Moldovan language led to the declaration by Mikhail Gorbachev, the last President of the erstwhile Soviet Union that the law and regulation by the Moldovan Parliament shall be null and void on the Pridnestrovian Moldovan Republic(PMR) also known as Transnistria.⁶ Thus, began the movement for the battle which was fought on the grounds of retaining the integrity and dignity of the Russian and Ukrainian speaking majority in the region of Transnistrian Republic.

The battle shaped itself in three main cities wherein various leaders took part with the citizens being supported externally by the erstwhile Soviet Army. The three cities and the areas surrounding them battled out the war which sought for the independence of the region and ensured the linguistic freedom of the people who lived in Majority in the region of Transnistria:

1. Cocieri-Dubasari
2. Cosnita

⁶ The fourth press statement of the Polit Buro of the Communist Party of Soviet Union, 22nd December 1990.

3. Tighina

The battles colluded over the period of time especially around the region of Cocieri and Dubasari region wherein the leaders fought the first battle. It is alleged that there has been a distinctive change that occurs in the process of developing the surrounding region of the city. The support to the PMR was given by the Soldiers who came from Rostov, Russia to the people as well as moved forward with the conceptual development of the structure that holds a quintessential power in terms of providing the arms to the residents. As it was heard that the soldiers were leaving for the city, they armed and provided for a structural establishment that prevented the soldiers from moving in. The police who supported the Moldovan Government had killed Igor Shipcenko that led to the movement of the political and defense military which created a sense of trigger amongst the citizens who revolted heavily against the police of the city. The mobility and the armed power was on such a high level that the Government sought the police to surrender before the militia. With the exchange of the military soldiers along with Lieutenant General Yakolev, who was arrested for treason and providing support to the PMR rebels, the situation which remained tensed, however, the city went under full control of the PMR militia.

Following the capture of the city, the Corcieri citizens got concerned and picked up weapons and prevented the further escalations by the PMR militants that involved in terms of taking or conquering of the lands. With the crucial fight excruciating between the locations and the vocal support for the leaders took action and the thus began the six-month long entrenchment war in the city of Corcieri.⁷

The battle in the region further took its own course of action which provides for a structure that has been effective and efficient at the same time which went ahead to further villages which are Cosnita, Piritia and Pohrebea wherein the capturing was comparatively easier than the other parts of the region. The support was enunciated at a greater scale when the former Vice-President of erstwhile Soviet Russia Alexander Rutskoy ensured the full support to the federal Republic of Transnistria.⁸

The final step that was transcending at the final stage of the war was the movement after the holding of negotiations in the city of Bender. The month of June 1992 was the focal point as

⁷ V. Grecu – "O viziune din focarul conflictului de la Dubăsari", page 65-68

⁸ Хроника конфликта в Приднестровско – Молдавской республике с 1988 по 2006 г.

many of the leaders moved to formalize the negotiations that were carried out to ensure the peace and harmony in the region. However, while the ceasefire agreement was supposed to be signed, there was a significant change in the action of the executive of the city of Bender as the police entered the city and started firing at the PMR militia and Cossack Regiments. The further escalation took place with the retaliation of the of the soldiers of the Cossack which resulted in collateral damages as well as a sense of panic was created amongst the citizens of Dubasari which was 11 km away from the former. The final announcement of a full-fledged attack was declared by Vice-President Rutskoj which suggested the full fledged attack by the Cossack and the PMR militia to enter into the field of Bender which turned out to be catastrophic for the Moldovan army which finally ended with the PMR re-capturing the land. The impact was made to be of the greater extent which was effective and affectionate towards the creation of such identities which still holds power to this date.

Aftermath:

With the demolition of the Moldovan army over the annexation and the warfare which was carried out post the downfall of Soviet Union showed that the Russians still held their power and their might over their rights. The ceasefire was finally signed between the Russian President Boris Yeltsin and the Moldovan President Mircea Sneuger which ended the war between the two countries and the region of Transnistria. Further, there was an establishment of a Joint Control Commission which was consisting of the Russian Army, Moldovan Army and PMR militias to establish Peace-keeping forces in the region of Transnistria and Moldova and ensure no further fights and breakouts take place. The commission was also to ensure free and fair movement of carrying goods through out the region as well as consider the importance of providing for the structure that would ensure freer transitions and transactions between various countries. The region of Transnistria turned out to be a center which held importance which was considered to be the idea of providing Autonomy to the region as well as provide for the idealistic approach which will be effective for the future purposes. The effect of the Russian army with proper training emerged the PMR militias to be victorious despite the aerial superiority that has been provided to the countries which consider and involve in the procedure of instructing a structure which was separately meant for the region which was surrounding itself with the Ukrainian and Russian population.

The idea of a unified Moldova and Romania was also shook to a certain extent as the Romanians felt they might be affected heavily by the threat of a Russian regime looming around the country which can be called as the potential Slavic threat.

Modern-Day Effect:

The present situation of the linguistic domination can be observed easily as the battles and various warfare have entrenched on the global map. The various wars which have been pertaining to the language has turned to be out to be a bitter sweet effect which can be called out as the Bi-partisan warfare structure and provide for the ideas that keep pertaining to the identical and linguistic chauvinism. The Balkans and the Baltic regions have been directly indulging themselves with the identical and linguistic warfare which can be distinctively seen in the Bosnian war as well as the Croat- Serbian war which one can see as one of the most impactful and a powerful effect towards the lives as well as the political disruptions that were taking place around the continent or even for that matter the identity for the existence in globe.

The ongoing conflict which is taking place between Russian Federation and Ukraine over the region of Donbas (the basin of the Donets river which has Ethnic Russians in majority) has involved a bloody conflict which is shedding nothing but blood and harm which is affecting the globe in all the three aspects which are the political, social and the economical conflicting structure.

Conclusion:

The end of the line which is presenting itself against all odds, one-of the shortest partisan warfare of the Slavic Europe resulted in a bigger odds of establishing as what can be called a structural improvement in the field of Rights entitlement and the fight for which one fights along the line. Some can conclusively come out victorious through various struggles and reformative actions and seek the result which is much needed, or for those who dream of providing a bigger and better structure for the ones who fight for a bigger battle. The others take their what belongs to them and find ways which might be incriminating to the security of their lives, however they provide a different solution to the table. The fight for the independence of the Transnistrian citizens. The battle was longing and providing a structure that would be helpful and provide for the key motivation which holds to the table of what

remains to be a catastrophically effecting the relations as well at the same time. The idea can be to consider better solutions to fight for the rights of such exigencies, however it remains to be seen whether one can understand and provide for the best way to come to conclusions. The war at such provides a perspective as well as the various strengths which one can determine, but it remains to be seen as to what can be provided for in the future.

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